

Crime Forecasting using Linear Regression and LSTM

Vasumalai Kannan A. Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai-625021
avasumalai@gmail.com

Introduction

Crime data analysis is an essential tool in understanding and combating criminal activities. It involves the collection, processing, and interpretation of data related to criminal incidents. Analysing crime data provides law enforcement agencies, policymakers, and communities with valuable insights into crime patterns, enabling them to make informed decisions and allocate resources effectively. This chapter explores the significance of crime data analysis, the methods used, and its impact on crime prevention and public safety.

Importance of Crime Data Analysis

Identifying Trends and Patterns: Crime data analysis helps identify trends and patterns in criminal activities. By examining data over time, analysts can pinpoint hotspots, high-risk areas, and common *modi operandi*, allowing law enforcement to focus their efforts strategically.

Resource Allocation: Law enforcement agencies can allocate their resources more efficiently. By understanding where and when crimes are likely to occur, they can deploy personnel and assets to deter criminal activities in specific areas or during specific timeframes.

Crime Prevention: Understanding the factors contributing to crime enables the development of effective prevention strategies. Data analysis helps identify root causes and risk factors, which can be addressed through community programs and policy changes.

Performance Evaluation: Police departments can assess the effectiveness of their strategies through data analysis. If a particular approach is not yielding positive results, adjustments can be made in a data-driven manner.

Community Engagement: Sharing crime data with the public fosters community engagement. By making data available to the public, communities can be more informed about local crime issues, potentially leading to a more active role in preventing crime.

The Need for Crime Forecasting

Proactive Policing: Traditional law enforcement models often rely on responding to crimes after they occur. Crime forecasting allows police agencies to adopt a proactive stance, preventing crimes before they happen by focusing resources in high-risk areas.

Resource Allocation: Law enforcement agencies operate with limited resources. Accurate crime forecasting helps optimize the allocation of personnel, patrol routes, and surveillance efforts, ensuring a more efficient use of available resources.

Community Engagement: Predictive policing fosters community engagement. By sharing insights and collaborating with communities, law enforcement can work with residents to address crime issues, build trust, and create safer neighborhoods.

Methodologies for Crime Forecasting

Time Series Analysis: Time series analysis involves examining historical crime data to identify trends, patterns, and seasonality. Techniques like ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) and Exponential Smoothing are commonly used in this approach.

Geospatial Analysis: Geospatial analysis focuses on the spatial distribution of crimes. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and spatial analysis tools are used to identify crime hotspots and analyze their characteristics.

Machine Learning: Machine learning techniques, such as Random Forests, XGBoost, and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), use historical crime data and various features (e.g., weather, demographic data) to build predictive models.

Predictive Analytics: Predictive analytics involves leveraging statistical models and algorithms to forecast crimes. These models often incorporate data from various sources, including social media, local events, and law enforcement activities.

In this work we used Chicago crime dataset from 2001 to 2020 which is available in the Chicago city portal and per capita GDP of Chicago metropolitan available from fred website. We used the Linear regressor and LSTM to forecast crime.

Linear Regression

We found the high negative correlation between the number of reported crime and per capita income of the Chicago metropolitan city. The p value after conducting ANOVA was lesser than .05 and we can accept the coefficient with the confidence level of 95%.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.939828821
R Square	0.883278213
Adjusted R Square	0.876793669
Standard Error	32324.46781
Observations	20

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	840451.3426	41519.09	20.24253	7.82E-14	753223	927679.7	753223	927679.7
X Variable 1	-9.807579191	0.840336	-11.671	7.88E-10	-11.5731	-8.0421	-11.5731	-8.0421

Granger Causality:

`grangers_causation_matrix(df, variables = df.columns)`

index	per_x	cme_x
per_y	1.0	0.0319
cme_y	0.019	1.0

When the granger causality test was conducted with the maximum lag of 4 we got the above matrix which shows the per capita series can be used to forecast the total crime.

LSTM

year=11, Predicted=265746.954951, Expected=261365.000000

1/1 [=====] - 0s 20ms/step

year=12, Predicted=252427.269763, Expected=212233.000000

Test RMSE: 18617.362

MAE:1444543.4511855245
 MAPE: 5.165167619242902

LSTM is a machine learning algorithm which can be used for time series data. Using LSTM the total crime was predicted after training the model with training data set and RMSE was calculated for the test data set.

Conclusion:

	Linear Regressions	LSTM
RMSE	30665.68273	18617.362
MAPE	8.284951	5.165167619242902

The above table shows the MAPE value for the two techniques used to forecast total number of crime at a year level granularity. The linear regression method uses the GDP & Per capita data, LSTM uses only the time series data. These two things can be used together to make a reliable prediction since these bring redundancy and diversity in the prediction. For any finer level of granularity, the ARIMA method can be used.

References:

1. <https://data.cityofchicago.org>
2. <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/PCRGMP16980>